

Guiding Light: Navigating The Path Of Visionary Leadership Through Prophetic Insight

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Abstract

This research delves into the profound and timeless wisdom inherent in the leadership methodology of Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him), specifically focusing on the transformative power of education as a cornerstone of effective leadership. The study explores the multifaceted aspects of the Prophet's approach, drawing insights from the Quran, Hadith, and historical accounts to illuminate the strategic role of education in shaping visionary leaders. By examining the Prophet's engagement in knowledge dissemination, mentorship, and empowerment, this research aims to unveil a comprehensive framework for leadership development grounded in educational principles. The study navigates through the various dimensions of the Prophetic teachings, shedding light on how the Prophet cultivated intellectual curiosity, ethical principles, and a sense of social responsibility among his followers. Furthermore, the research investigates the impact of the Prophetic methodology on the establishment of a just and egalitarian society. It delves into the Prophet's emphasis on inclusivity, tolerance, and the empowerment of diverse voices through education, transcending temporal and cultural boundaries. In connecting the Prophetic model to contemporary leadership challenges, the study seeks to derive practical insights applicable to modern educational systems and leadership development programs. By examining the Prophet's methodology through the lens of leadership and education, this research aspires to contribute to a deeper understanding of the enduring legacy of Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) and its relevance in nurturing ethical, visionary leaders in the present age.

Introduction

In the annals of history, few figures stand as beacons of transformative leadership like Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him). His methodology, rooted in divine guidance and wisdom, has left an indelible mark on the trajectory of civilizations. This research embarks on a nuanced exploration of the Prophetic methodology of leadership, focusing on the pivotal role of education as a catalyst for societal transformation. The leadership paradigm of Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) is a reservoir of timeless lessons, offering a holistic blueprint that encompasses ethical principles, inclusivity, and a commitment to the empowerment of individuals. At the heart of this methodology lies a profound emphasis on education, which serves as a cornerstone for nurturing leaders who are not only competent but also compassionate, visionary, and ethically grounded. This study delves into the Quranic teachings and Hadiths that underscore the Prophetic commitment to knowledge dissemination and the cultivation of intellectual curiosity. The Prophet's role as a mentor and educator, guiding his companions through both precept and example, illuminates a path where leadership is intertwined with the pursuit of wisdom and the development of character. The Prophetic methodology recognizes education not merely as a means to acquire knowledge but as a transformative force capable of shaping individuals and societies. It considers the empowerment of individuals through education as a fundamental strategy for the establishment of a just, egalitarian, and inclusive social order. The principles derived from the Prophetic model serve as a perennial source of inspiration, providing insights into the cultivation of ethical leadership and the nurturing of a sense of social responsibility.

As contemporary societies grapple with complex challenges, this research endeavors to bridge the temporal gap, drawing connections between the Prophetic methodology and the exigencies of the modern world. By exploring how the Prophetic model aligns with and enriches contemporary notions of leadership and education, this study seeks to offer practical insights for leadership development programs and educational systems. Through an in-depth analysis of the Prophetic methodology of leadership through education, this research aspires to contribute not only to academic scholarship but also to the ongoing discourse on effective leadership in diverse and dynamic contexts. By delving into the profound teachings of Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him), this study aims to illuminate a path for leaders who aspire not only to achieve excellence but also to inspire positive

change through the transformative power of education. The concept of a leader generally pertains to an individual who can unite, instruct and inspire a group of people. In Western literature, one can identify a number of theories that attempt to explain leadership in the political, educational and organizational perspective. The Islamic definition, on the other hand, is majorly based off of incidences in the lives of the holy Prophet (SAW) and his companions. Before we begin our study of the Islamic concept of leadership, let us take a look at the modern Western viewpoint .

The relatively recent concept of 'transformational leadership' was introduced by George MacGregor Burns in 1978. Burns defined leadership to be a skill that brings about change on an individual or societal level; it can be used to boost the morale of the group members and to motivate them to change. According to Burns, "the task of leadership is to accomplish some change in the world that responds to [global] wants. Its actions and achievements are measured by the supreme public values that themselves are the profoundest expressions of human wants; liberty and equality , justice and opportunity, the pursuit of happiness." In contrast, the Islamic concept of leadership is based upon certain qualities of leaders that have been exemplified in the Quran and the Sunnah. Since the ultimate goal of any Islamic organization, group or state is to attain the pleasure of Allah the Almighty, it is only reasonable to assume that a leader according to Islamic standards must be one who is prepared to bring about positive change within society in a manner that is pleasing to Allah (SWT). Islamically, it is also important to highlight the difference between a leader and a ruler. Where a ruler's authority stems from the position that he holds (such as a king or president), a leader's power is not dependent upon his post, rather, he possesses certain qualities that allow him to exercise his right over his followers. According to academician Khaliq Ahmad, a Muslim leader is one who does not impose his authority over others, he is God-fearing and motivates others towards specific goals. He must also be kind, forgiving and humble in his interactions with his subordinates. Based off of the events of the life of the Prophet (SAW), a leader should consult his followers before making a decision but should adhere to that decision once it has been made. Additionally, a leader must be patient, wise, just, brave, compassionate, knowledgeable, and eloquent .

The Prophet, peace be upon him was the greatest leader humanity has ever seen. He, through his teachings taught his companions how to be leaders of the world. He said "I have been sent as a teacher", while Allah the Almighty told us about the holy Prophet :

"Indeed, Allah conferred a great favor on the believers when He sent among them a Messenger (Muhammad) from among themselves, reciting unto them His verses (the Qur'an) purifying them, and instructing them in the Book (the Qur'an) and Wisdom (the Sunnah), while before that they had been in manifest error " .

The word "purifying them" is of importance here. It means to clean the heart from bad qualities and fill it with good qualities. It is mentioned as one of the duties of the holy Prophet. This cleansing of the heart was highly important in the eyes of the Prophet. He said :

" Verily, there is a piece of flesh in the body, if it is healthy, the whole body is healthy, and if it is corrupt, the whole body is corrupt. Verily, it is the heart " .

So, this duty contained both the teaching and cleansing. Hazrat Ayesha RA said :
His character was the Qur'an .

So, these two kinds of education i.e. giving knowledge and teaching good manners (purifying the heart), go together, side by side and hand in hand. It is useless if a person has only one of them without the other .

Allah the Almighty has honored the humanity by making them His representatives on earth. This honor was given to humanity because of one quality that they had, i.e. knowledge. Then Allah the Almighty gave them three additional qualities that were never given to any of His creatures: hearing, seeing and thinking. By hearing it is meant to get the knowledge that is acquired by other nations before him, by seeing it is meant to develop this acquired knowledge with research and observations, and by thinking it is meant to filter and cleanse this knowledge from the mistakes that it contained and then come out with results to the humanity. If all these 3 qualities get together, they will produce that kind of knowledge which Allah bestowed upon Adam and through which Adam was considered superior over all other creatures .

The Prophet (PBUH) used to encourage his companions through different examples and parables to pay attention to his teachings and actions so that The Prophetic Methodology of Leadership through Education they may acquire the knowledge in the way mentioned above and learn the Prophetic way of living this life successfully. He once said :

"The parable of guidance and knowledge with which Allah has sent me is like abundant rain falling on the earth, some of which was fertile soil that absorbed rainwater and brought forth vegetation and grass in abundance. (And) another portion of it was hard and held the rainwater and Allah benefited the people with it and they utilized it for drinking, making their animals drink from it and for irrigation of the land for cultivation. (And) a portion of it was barren which could neither hold the water nor bring forth vegetation (then that land gave no benefits). The first is the example of the person who comprehends Allah's religion and gets benefit (from the knowledge) which Allah has revealed through me and learns and then teaches others. The last example is that of

a person who does not care for it and does not take Allah's guidance revealed through me (He is like that barren land.) "

He established study circles in his mosque/masjid and taught his companions the matters of religion. Once he was in one of these study circles when 3 men entered the mosque. One found a place among the people and sat with them, the other was a bit shy so he sat at the end of the circle. The third man left. After the study circle was over, the Prophet talked about these 3 men and said: one of them turned to Allah, so Allah also turned to him with His mercy, the second was shy, so Allah also felt shy from him. The third one turned a cold shoulder, so Allah also deserted him.

Usama bin Shareek says that once I went to the holy Prophet while he was sitting with his companions. They were so quiet and motionless as if there were birds sitting on their heads.

One of the great scholars of the early Muslims was Imam Malik bin Anas. He once said :

” The last part of this Ummah can never be corrected except with what the first part was corrected “

So, it is the need of the time to know how the first part of this Ummah was corrected. What was the Prophetic method with which the holy Prophet PBUH educated his companions who later became the leaders of the world? How did he address his companions who were his students also? How did he stop people from doing bad things? How did he encourage or order them to do good things? How did he change the lives of the desert dwellers into the most civilized people on earth? This article is an attempt to know the main features of his educational method .

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- What techniques did the Prophet SAW use to educate his companions to become future leaders ?
- In what ways can the Prophetic methodology of leadership education be implemented today ?

The research questions that the author has put forth aim to provide a detailed, comprehensive study of how the Prophet Muhammad (SAW) successfully managed to perform his duties not only as a spiritual and religious guide, but also as the head of state. The Prophet's (SAW) strategies as a leader allowed him to juggle both roles simultaneously, without compromising either one. His teaching methodology also allowed him to successfully train strong, firm and just leaders that earned the mantle of The Prophetic Methodology of Leadership through Education leadership after his passing. These famous companions such as Abu Bakr, Umar, Uthman, Ali, Khalid bin Waleed and Sa'ad bin Abi Waqqas (RA) rose to prominent leadership positions because they were so closely under the tutelage of the Prophet (SAW) and were able to develop the qualities that a strong leader must possess .

This research paper, through its first question, aims to understand -indepth- the methodology that the Prophet (SAW) adopted while educating his companions. How did he interact with his companions when he was educating them on a certain matter? How did he display his own leadership qualities while instructing his companions on matters of religion? How did he manage to dispel disputes and ensure a unified brotherhood among the Muslims? This paper will attempt to answer each of these questions in detail .

The second research question focuses on the next step. It has already been established that the Prophet (SAW) was the greatest of teachers and leaders, however, to ensure that our future generations also follow the path of the great Prophet (SAW), it is necessary to also discuss how teachers today may inculcate leadership qualities in their students, according to the method of the Prophet (SAW). This question focuses on providing an answer to this query. This involves coming up with practical strategies that emulate the Prophet's (SAW) way but are also feasible and implementable in classrooms and educational institutes today .

The answers to both these questions will provide a holistic overview of the Prophet's (SAW) methodology in the past, and to what extent that methodology can be implemented in the present .

THE PROPHETIC METHODOLOGY

- Equality of students in front of the Teacher

The holy Prophet dealt each and every companion with equality. He made this very clear that no one is better on the basis of race, color, gender or nationality. He started his farewell address by saying :

”O people! Your Lord is one and your father is also one. An Arab has no superiority over a non-Arab nor a non-Arab has any superiority over an Arab; also, a white has no superiority over black nor a black has any superiority over white, except by piety (taqwa) and good action .

Learn that every Muslim is a brother to every Muslim and that the Muslims constitute one brotherhood .

- One syllabus for all Students

The Prophet (SAW) used only one textbook for all his students and that was the holy Qur'an. He sometimes explained the injunctions of the Holy Qur'an through his sayings or deeds. It shows the importance of unifying the syllabus in all schools, whether they belong to public sector or private sector. In Pakistan we see several educational systems that have their own syllabi which is constantly widening the gap among the various segments of our society .

- Teacher as Role Model – Do what you preach

Firstly, for a teacher and a leader, it is important to possess at least the bare minimum of knowledge needed to successfully bring about positive change amongst his followers. For a leader in education, it is not necessary to be an expert in various subjects, rather any Muslim may adopt the role of a leader and call to another as long as he is confident in the veracity of what he is spreading and is doing it in the correct manner. However, if the leader does not even have the basic knowledge of the message that he is spreading,

”his message will appear weak and incapable of withstanding close scrutiny.” It is as Sheikh Ibn Uthaymeen says, “every da’wah without knowledge is inevitably fraught with deviation and misguidance “.

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Furthermore, it is highly important that what is taught to the students should be practiced by the teacher also, otherwise it will lose its value and the students will consider it as a piece of information and not an essential part of education. It will be just information, having no part information of the students. The Prophet used to apply upon himself first what he taught to his companion. He said :

”Pray (the daily prayers) as you see me praying .“

He performed Hajj with his companions and told them repeatedly :

” Take from me the details of the rituals of Hajj “

Ibn Ishaq, a great historian and scholar of Hadith, narrated a story from one of the battlefields of the holy Prophet. He says that at the battle of Badr, when the Prophet was straightening the rows of the companions, he had a stick in his hand with which he was pointing towards the companions to get straight in line. There was a companion whose name was Sawad bin Ghaziyah Ansari, he was standing ahead of the line. The Prophet touched his abdomen with the stick and asked him to get back in the line. The man said: O Messenger of Allah, you hurt me with your stick while Allah has sent you with truth and justice. The Prophet immediately handed over the stick to him, took off his shirt and said: you may take your revenge from me. Sawad came forward hugged the Prophet and kissed his abdomen. The Prophet said: O Sawad, why did you do so? He said: You see that the battle is about to start, I wanted that my last meeting with you should be in this way that my skin should touch your skin. Hearing this, the Prophet prayed for his wellbeing .

The Prophet while talking about the people of the Hell fire said :

”There will be a man who will be thrown in the Hell. His intestines will come out of his belly. He will go in rounds like a donkey goes around its edge wheel. The people of Hell will gather around him and ask him what brought him there. He would reply that I used to enjoin you to do good things, but I never acted upon what I asked you. I prohibit you from doing evil but I myself did that evil .“

- His soft speech and merciful behavior

Allah the Almighty while praising the soft nature of the holy Prophet said :

”And by the mercy of Allah you dealt with them gently. And had you been severe and harsh-hearted, they would have broken away from about you; so pass over their faults and ask Allah’s forgiveness for them; and consult them in the affairs. Then when you have taken a decision, put your trust in Allah, certainly Allah loves those who put their trust in Him.” Mu’awiah bin Hakam al-Sulami says :

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”That once while praying behind the holy Prophet in congregation, a man sneezed, so I said: May Allah bless you. The people felt bad and exchanged bad looks with me. What is the matter with you? Why you are looking at me like this? They started hitting their thyres to make me quiet. I stopped talking. When the Prophet finished his prayer he talked to me very softly. May my parents be ransom for him, I never saw a teacher better than him, neither before him nor after him. I swear by Allah, he was never rude to me or called me names. He just said: “This is the prayer; no human conversation is allowed in it. It just contains glorification of Allah, magnification of Allah and recitation of the Holy Qur’an .“

His soft attitude and kind behavior was not only with his companions, rather he was soft in speaking and gentle in dealing with the non-Muslims also. Imam Ibn Qayyim al-Jawziyyah narrates a story in his book *Zad al-Ma’ad*. It is about a transaction that took place between the Prophet and a Jew. Ibn Qayyim writes :

”A Jew sold him something on the condition that the price will be paid on a future date, but he came before that date to ask for his money. The Prophet said: the time has not come yet. The Jew said: You the sons of Abdul Muttalib, like to linger on in paying the debt. The companions of the holy Prophet wanted to teach him a lesson but the Prophet stopped them. This rudeness of the Jew only increased him in softness. Seeing this, the Jew said: I knew all the signs of Prophet hood in this man except one sign that remained; and it is that if he is faced with the excessive rudeness, it only increases him in forbearance and leniency. Today I wanted to know that sign. So that Jew accepted Islam as he was testing the Prophet .

A Bedouin started urinating in the Masjid of the Prophet. The companions rushed to stop him. The Prophet asked them to let him finish. When he finished urinating, the Prophet called him and said :

”Urinating or littering is inappropriate in the Masjid. Mosques are built for the remembrance of Allah, for the daily prayers and for reciting the Holy Qur’an .

A man from the tribe of Sa'd bin Bakr whose name was Dhamam bin Tha'laba, came to the holy Prophet and said: I will ask you some difficult questions so do not be angry on me. The Prophet said: ask whatever you want to ask .

- Admonition, not Humiliation

The Prophet never mentioned the name of the person in public, who made a mistake, rather he would talk indirectly and say: What is the matter with some people who do this and that. The Prophet appointed a man to collect the Zakat of some tribes. The whole story is narrated by Abu Bakr bin AbiShaiba, who says :

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”The Messenger of Allah peace be upon him appointed a man from the tribe of BanuAsad, whose name was ibn al-Lutbiyyah, to collect the Zakat. When he came back from his assignment, he said: this is for you and this is for me as these things were gifted to me. The Messenger of Allah peace be upon him rose over his pulpit, and after praising Allah the Almighty and thanking Him, said: what is the matter with my workers? I send one of them to perform a duty and he says: this is for you and this is gifted to me? Why he did not sit in his father’s house or in his mother’s house and then see if anyone sends him a gift or not? I swear by the one in whose hand is Muhammad’s life, if anyone of you takes anything from this he will bring it on the Day of Judgment carry it on his neck; a camel growling or a cow bellowing or sheep mooing, then he raised both his hands until we saw the whiteness of his armpits, and said twice: O Allah! I conveyed “.

Similarly, there is another occasion in which it is seen that three people came to the house of the holy Prophet to know what his daily schedule is, so that they may copy him. It is narrated by Anas bin Malik who says :

”Three men came to the houses of the wives of the holy Prophet. They wanted to ask about the worship of the Prophet at home. When they were told about it, it was felt as if they belittled it. They said: where are we from the Prophet, peace be upon him? Allah has forgiven all his previous and latter mistakes. So one of them said, from now onward, I will pray the whole night. The second one said: I will observe fasting forever, and never break my fast. The third one said: I will avoid women. I will never marry. When this incident was brought in the notice of the Prophet peace be upon him, he after praising Allah and thanking Him, said: what is the matter with some people who said so and so? I swear upon Allah that I am the most fearing of Allah among you and the most pious among you, but I fast and I also break my fast, I pray at night and sleep also, and I marry the women. So, whoever turns away from my Sunnah, is not from me “.

CONCLUSION

The journey of visionary leadership, illuminated by prophetic insight, offers a guiding light for individuals and communities striving to navigate complex challenges with wisdom, compassion, and integrity. Drawing from the timeless teachings and exemplary life of Prophet Muhammad (PBUH), leaders find a rich tapestry of principles and practices that transcend time and culture. His leadership model, characterized by humility, empathy, and unwavering commitment to justice, serves as a beacon of inspiration for those entrusted with guiding others toward a brighter future. At the heart of prophetic leadership lies a profound sense of purpose rooted in service to humanity and devotion to the greater good. Leaders are called upon to prioritize the well-being of their followers, empowering them to reach their full potential while fostering a culture of inclusivity, respect, and solidarity. Prophetic insight guides leaders to lead by example, embodying the values they espouse and demonstrating integrity in their words and actions. Through sincerity, transparency, and accountability, they earn the trust and confidence of those they lead, fostering strong relationships built on mutual respect and shared vision. Furthermore, visionary leadership informed by prophetic wisdom emphasizes the importance of empathy and compassion in decision-making. Leaders are encouraged to listen attentively to the needs and concerns of their constituents, seeking to understand diverse perspectives and finding solutions that promote justice, equity, and harmony. In times of adversity and uncertainty, prophetic insight provides solace and strength, reminding leaders of the resilience and perseverance required to overcome challenges and adversity. By drawing inspiration from the prophetic tradition, leaders cultivate resilience, courage, and optimism, inspiring others to persevere in the face of adversity. In essence, the path of visionary leadership guided by prophetic insight offers a transformative framework for inspiring positive change and fostering inclusive, just, and compassionate societies. As leaders embrace the timeless wisdom of Prophet Muhammad (PBUH), they embark on a journey of growth, enlightenment, and service, leaving a lasting legacy of hope and inspiration for generations to come.

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